

INTERNATIONAL DUBLIN UNIVERSITY
Department of Forensic Informatics Engineering

**CHALLENGES IN SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE IN CLOUD COMPUTING
AND ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL FORENSIC RESEARCH**

MASTER'S THESIS

Thesis advisor: Dr. Murat Gezer

February 2022

Prepared By: Burak ÇINAR

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This study, titled “CHALLENGES IN SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE IN CLOUD COMPUTING AND ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL FORENSIC RESEARCH” presented by Burak ÇINAR as MASTER'S THESIS, was evaluated by us in accordance with the relevant provisions of the International Dublin University Education and Training Directive and was deemed worthy of defense. It was found to be successful by unanimity/majority of votes.

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ABSTRACT

CHALLENGES IN SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE IN CLOUD COMPUTING AND ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL FORENSIC RESEARCH

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Although cloud computing is at a very important point in the field of information technologies and the opportunities it offers, the orientation towards cloud computing has been increasing recently. In addition to the opportunities offered by cloud computing, it also contains some risks. This situation also leads to an increase in concerns about the security of data transferred in the cloud environment. However, the importance of forensic investigations carried out on cloud computing is also increasing. Within the scope of this study, the basics and types of cloud computing were focused on, and its advantages and disadvantages were identified. However, within the scope of the study, problems in the cloud computing architecture were identified and evaluations were made and the analysis of digital forensics research was carried out.

Key Words: Analysis, Cloud Computing, Digital Forensics.

INTRODUCTION

Subject of Research

Significant changes are taking place in the field of computers day by day. In the era that started with computers with large dimensions but limited functions, computers with high processing power and portable characteristics were adopted. With the emergence of computers, an important pioneering experience has been experienced in the world of informatics. Personal computers have become widespread in all areas of life, whether for business or personal purposes. Over time, the speed of personal computers increased, and their size became smaller and later, portable computers and mobile phones emerged. With the advent of the Internet, significant developments have occurred in the communication and exchange of data. Data is stored in certain places and started to be presented to a wide range of users thanks to the internet network. In this process, services have emerged as well as new web technologies. Today, internet applications have increased and business applications have started to become widespread. During this period, users' requests, applications, use of a figure independent of time, place and platforms began to develop. In order to respond to these requests, a new formation called cloud computing has emerged. Although it is based on cloud computing service architecture, it provides access to data and applications in a figure independent of devices, and provides the opportunity to be scaled in an easy figure by enabling applications to become widespread. Forensic investigations in the cloud are becoming a complex situation. Since the traditional forensic approach cannot define the problems encountered in the cloud computing environment in a clear figure, forensic computing is moving towards the cloud. In this study, the problems experienced in cloud computing architecture and the analysis of digital forensic studies are emphasized.

Purpose of the research

Within the scope of this study, it is aimed to identify and evaluate the problems of cloud computing architecture and to conduct a research on the analysis of digital forensics research.

Importance of Research

Cloud computing system has a very flexible structure. Therefore, the tools and processes for the collection of evidence in forensic investigations carried out in the cloud environment should be in the same flexible structure. One of the important features of the cloud is the sharing of resources among many users. Therefore, during investigations, it is important to distinguish only the part targeted by the investigation from different users on the same physical resources. Within the scope of this study, it is important in terms of detecting the problems experienced in cloud computing architecture and performing the analysis of digital forensic studies and because it is an example for future studies in the literature.

1. CLOUD COMPUTING

1.1. The Historical Process of Cloud Computing

Cloud computing is defined as the delivery of IT resources via the internet through different cloud service providers in a paid figure within the scope of the demands of individuals or institutions that need the resources of information technologies (Avram, 2014). Instead of buying physical servers and establishing data centers in different locations in terms of disaster scenarios, these services are served via the internet. In the current period, he started to work in a figure integrated with multiple cloud systems. In the era we live in, everything is connected to the internet and interacts with the tools that provide direct communication via the internet. Word devices write and store different data as well as read it. Systems that manage such operations in a common figure have also brought cloud computing. As of 2006, it has been accepted that new services are used for the first time with the concept of cloud, and it has become an area that develops in a dynamic figure with the development of new services and environments almost every year.

Cloud computing provides an infrastructure service that gives the power of interaction to digital devices such as mobile devices, smart watches or today's portable and internet-connected devices. The Internet of Things is accelerating emerging workspaces like big data and artificial intelligence, as well as managing and storing it. For this reason, accelerating the current industry dynamics in these areas combines this with the take, apply and manage model, which removes the most important obstacles on the way to digital transformation (Sunyaev, 2020).

The benefits of cloud communication are given below (Sunyaev, 2020):

- It manages the said services by taking the physical servers or data centers located at different points in the scattered figure.
- It provides backup of servers or data centers.
- It lists the possible solutions that can prevent disaster scenarios.

- It provides a user interface to the user or companies within the scope of the opportunity of the cloud service provider from which it has received service.

- It sees the servers located at completely separate points from each other as a whole and finds the opportunity to see that they communicate with different applications or services over each other.

- Faster than normal servers or internet networks in terms of speed in high-scale services

- It can serve in special events such as artificial intelligence machine learning without hardware facilities or any infrastructure service.

As of 1963, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) allocated a budget of \$3 million for the MAC project. Although the budget is the product of a project designed to multiply the given budget resources, the budget provided allows MIT to use a computer by two or more people at the same time. Thus, it was requested to perform pair-programming steps. A system called archaic computer that can do this simultaneously has been developed. Today, it has been seen as the most primitive structure of the cloud concept. The computer system in question, which two or more individuals can access, has brought forward that there is a way to share the physical space and virtualize it. Here, the foundations of a new technology called "Virtualization or Virtualization" were laid. However, at that time, virtualization only allowed more than one sharing and had a limited meaning. In 1980 and later, its scope was expanded and until the current period, computer systems continued to expand to the figure that would be in the first place (Swain, 2015).

By 1960, J. C. R. Licklider had contributed to the development of the Advanced Research Projects Agency Network, an underdeveloped version of the Internet. In addition to being a JCR computer scientist, he argued that every individual on the planet could be connected to each other through computers. The "Intergalactic Computer Network" known as the Internet is necessary for access to the cloud.

ARPANET has expanded over time with the state support it has received and the devoted work of JCR and has made a name for itself in the 70s.

Between 1970 and 1970, the narrower and unexplained meaning of the scope of virtualization began to change since 1970. It is based on the creation of a virtual machine that is a fully functional communication system and acts like a real computer. The term virtualization has grown and turned into a service tool. Virtual servers are installed on physical servers, saving money and costs from anywhere. In addition, it has developed in parallel with the internet. It emerged as a critical concept that formed the basis of the current cloud communication infrastructure in 1990-2000.

In 1990 and after, cloud communication continued to develop in an abstract figure during these years. It was built on the concept of virtualization but remained in the air. When cloud communication was considered within the scope of the technological infrastructures of that period, it gained a new perspective and it was agreed that it was a new mechanism and to make things easier.

As of 1991, the internet was discovered and the popularity of communication and applications increased. Therefore, mandatory fields have been created in case they interact with each other. These developments have not only improved the cloud ecosystem, but also enabled large companies to make R&D investments in the field and become the pioneers of this growing sector.

In 1999, Salesforce integrated cloud communication into its own systems and had a great impact around the world. It has delivered the activities it has given mostly on the CRM field to the end user and has realized these thanks to the internet. The use of the internet has started to increase around the world and it has been proven that the application is accessible in every region of the world. It has been observed that this situation provides great savings in terms of time and in terms of cost, using the application without installation anywhere is positive because it contributes to the budget.

In 2000 and 2006, an increase was observed in the variety of services provided to end users via the Internet in the 2000s. Everyone has taken their place in the accelerating sector and the general public has started to establish their infrastructure via the internet. Amazon, which will be mentioned a lot later on, introduced its web-based retail services. Web-based retail services, on the other hand, have evolved and created a great deal of flexibility. Existing computers have used the servers very effectively and have received their feedback.

As of 2006, Amazon Web Services, which was revolutionary for the following periods, were introduced to the market. However, Amazon websites have begun to offer different services to home Amazon's customers. In the years when the cloud computing name was very popular, it introduced its new service called "Amazon S3 Cloud Storage", one of the first services of Amazon. As can be understood from the name of the service in question, it provided a simple figure storage service in an online figure. Later, it introduced its second service called "Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud - Amazon EC2)". The service in question provides the rental of virtual computers and allows users or companies to run their own programs or applications. In addition, it offered different cloud-based services, including storage, computing and human intelligence, from Amazon Web Services sites called "Amazon Mechanical Turk" (Surbiryala and Rong 2019).

2008 and Google, trying to take its place in the cloud sector and having a strong infrastructure, introduced a service called "Google Document services". Although the services in question are of two different types, Google offered the electronic E-Table service in terms of innovation. Within the scope of E-Table services, documents can be written, recorded or edited. Google has done this on a pay-as-you-go principle and rents the e-Table area. Google bought the "Google E-Tables" service from another company in order to catch up with the market and not be late. He later bought Writely and allowed the transfer of these documents. While the aforementioned developments continued, selection was made according to the types found. Private cloud technology started in 2008, but has not made much progress. Although public cloud systems are attractive, they have not been used much due to concerns that there may be security vulnerabilities to users or companies. For this reason, large companies such as AWS, Microsoft, OpenStack, which are among the cloud service providers that see the

demand for private Cloud, have improved their investments and diversity in the private Cloud field.

Two big rival companies, Microsoft and IBM, which dominated the sector in 2010-2011 and late, continued their development in order to take their place in the field of cloud computing. Initially, in 2010, Microsoft introduced the Azure Cloud company. Later in 2011 IBM introduced the Cloud System. IBM actually announced the IBM Smart Cloud service to support the cultural thinking project Smart Planet. During these years, the Microsoft company has advertised television and cloud systems in many areas on its social media accounts. Later, Apple announced the "iCloud" service, thinking that the industry was heating up and that it needed to make any moves. Thanks to this service, users have introduced that they can store their own photos, texts, pictures, music, videos and different kinds of information within a certain limit. Along with these developments, the concept of Hybrid Cloud, which will be included later between Private cloud and Public cloud, was announced in 2008. With this technology introduced in 2001, it was stated that the load could be moved between the private cloud and the public cloud and that it could be forwarded to the public cloud and private cloud when desired.

In 2014, cloud computing started to take figures more and more. It has started to be used by many companies or users by developing its most basic features. However, everyone was concerned about safety. Ensuring cloud security has become a rapidly growing service for users who purchase cloud services. Cloud security has greatly advanced and is now anticipated to provide protection comparable to a traditional IT security system. With all this, the issue of security has become a concern of many cloud users.

In 2016, Oracle introduced a system called "Oracle Cloud Infrastructure", which includes three main elements in cloud computing, IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service), PaaS (Platform as a Service) and SaaS (Software as a Service) in order to maintain its position in the industry. With these services, which have different advantages and disadvantages compared to other clouds, the race to prioritize cloud systems in the world has gained a different dimension. Cloud composition has been used frequently by software developers. Previously, while providing a different

environment to developers, it has pushed developers to develop on cloud computing systems and to use services in a nested figure. The cloud saw the profit potential in this part and by offering many service options, it was possible for the developers to develop applications running in an integrated figure together with cloud computing systems.

In 2017, containers in the form of lightweight technology for the virtualization of applications have been very successful in managing applications in the cloud computing system (Pahl, Brogi et al., 2017). Those who produce in a similar figure in this field have offered different technologies to their service. Among the most well-known examples in the form of containers is the "Kubernetes" technology developed through Google in 2014. With this product, which was promoted as open source, it became easier to manage applications and was accepted through the market. Both can be viewed side by side with Docker. Kubernetes is expressed as a container orchestration system designed for the distribution of applications in the cloud computing system in the shortest figure. Later, different container models emerged through different production providers.

After 2019, cloud computing, along with the COVID-19 virus, which affects the lives of all people, has led to doing all the operations of the pandemic and quarantine processes from home. However, the desire for the internet and the emergence of different new products and concepts and physical use have shown that it can be interrupted for any reason. Considering the intensity of e-commerce shopping and the intensity of this situation, it is predicted that it will develop and grow even more in the pandemic process.

Architecture of Cloud Computing

Cloud computing architecture according to the reference architecture created through NIST:

- Cloud consumer
- Service provider

- Cloud auditor
- Cloud agent
- The figure that will be the cloud carrier consists of five actors.

The cloud computing reference architecture prepared through NIST is given in the figure 1.1 given below.

Figure 1.1: Stack diagram for cloud computing reference architecture

Bibliography: (Hogan et al., 2011:6-11)

Cloud Consumer: It is the main stakeholder within the scope of cloud computing services. If the cloud consumer is a cloud provider, they maintain a business relationship and represent the person or organization using the service from a cloud provider. The cloud consumer requests an appropriate service from a service catalog from a cloud provider and uses the service by entering into service contracts with the cloud provider.

Table 1.1: Consumer activities according to cloud service models

Service Type	Cloud Consumer Activities
Software as a service	The business process uses the application or service on behalf of its operations.
Platform as a service	It is defined as the service where the development, testing, distribution and management of applications in the cloud computing structure takes place.
Infrastructure as a Service	It is defined as the service created, managed and monitored on behalf of IT infrastructure operations.

Bibliography: (Hogan et al., 2011:6-11)

Cloud consumers are required to pay for the services rendered and adjust the payment accordingly. SLAs are required to address the technical performance needs of cloud consumers that cloud providers have met. The SLA includes the terms of service quality, security and measures to correct performance errors.

Service Level Agreement (SLA): An agreement for the service level that will provide access to information during technical repairs due to service failures. Cloud provider SLAs may also list promises that are not made in a clear figure to consumers, that is, restrictions and responsibilities that cloud consumers must accept. Cloud consumers do not have the right to choose cloud providers with good pricing and favorable conditions, but they can also apply it as they wish (Hogan et al., 2011: 6-11).

Cloud Auditor: It is defined as the party that makes independent reviews of cloud service auditing to express their opinions. The purpose of the audit is to review objective evidence and verify compliance with standards. Cloud auditors evaluate security controls, privacy impact, performance, and compliance with service-level contracting parameters of services provided through cloud providers. However, on behalf of the security audit, a cloud auditor can evaluate the security controls in the information system in order to determine to what extent the audits are implemented correctly, work in a targeted figure, and produce the desired result for meeting the security needs on behalf of the system (Hogan et al., 2011: 6-11).

Cloud Provider: Cloud providers are defined as the person or organization responsible for providing cloud services to the required authorities. Among the responsibilities of the cloud providers, it makes arrangements in order to provide the necessary information processing infrastructures for the provision of services and to manage all these, to run the software that performs the services and to offer all the services it provides to the consumers via the internet. However, the actor responsible for security and privacy is defined as the cloud provider (Hogan et al., 2011: 6-11).

Table 1.2: Activities of providers by cloud service figures

Service Type	Cloud Provider Responsibilities
Software as a Service	It is installed in the cloud infrastructure of the provided software applications. Maintenance is carried out at the right time intervals and support is provided.
Platform as a Service	It provides and manages cloud infrastructure and middleware to cloud users. It also provides tools for development, distribution and management on behalf of its users.
Infrastructure as a Service	In the form of a service, the software provides and manages the storage of information to its users, the network and the environment in which it is hosted, and the cloud infrastructure.

Bibliography: (Hogan et al., 2011:6-11)

Figure 1.2: Services undertaken by cloud providers

Source: (Hogan et al., 2011:6-11)

Cloud Broker: Once cloud computing has evolved, the integration of cloud services can become too complicated for cloud consumers to manage. Cloud consumers want cloud services in cloud agents instead of interacting directly with cloud providers. Therefore, cloud computing requires cloud agents. A cloud agent is

defined as a participant or entity that manages the use, performance and distribution of cloud services and negotiates the relationship between cloud providers and cloud consumers.

In a comprehensive figure, the services provided by cloud brokers are examined under three headings:

- **Service Brokerage:** The cloud broker develops certain capabilities and provides value-added services to cloud consumers and enhances certain services. Optimization manages access to cloud services as well as identity management, performance reporting, advanced secure services.
- **Service Aggregation:** Cloud agents integrate multiple services as well as merge them into more new services. Agents enable the integration of data and secure movement of data between cloud consumers and multi-cloud providers.
- **Service Arbitrage:** Expects a cluster of services, except that the aggregated services are not fixed. Service arbitrage means that brokers can flexibly choose services from multiple institutions or organizations.

Cloud Carrier: It acts as an intermediary between cloud consumers and cloud providers that connects and transports cloud services. Cloud carriers provide access through consumer networks, telecommunications, and other access equipment. In the distribution of cloud services, it is usually provided by network and telecommunications operators or transportation vehicles. In this case, transition agents are used in commercial organizations to take their place in the physical mobile storage environment. In order to provide consistent services at the SLA level that cloud providers offer to cloud consumers, they should provide private and secure link connections with the cloud carrier.

1.2. Features of Cloud Computing

The main features of cloud computing are explained below.

Outsourcing

Instead of using the physical hardware in the users' own environments, cloud service providers are responsible for the management and use of the said hardware.

Scalability

Applications running in cloud communication are normally in a highly scalable state. Applicants who request resources from cloud service providers can add or remove these resources in a manual figure, or the application can be configured in a figure that will scale in an automatic figure (Swain 2015).

Accessibility

From any location where the internet network is located in an uninterrupted figure or a stable figure, continuous calculation, storage, server and analysis processes can be accessed through cloud computing.

Virtualization

Since hardware resources in cloud computing systems are generally virtual, these virtual resources are shared by multiple users to increase efficiency. Multiple virtual servers can be installed on a single physical server, and virtual servers can be connected to a single virtual server center.

Beyond As You Use

Cloud computing stands out in terms of its flexibility and one of the most critical elements is the flexible payment system. In this case, it is performed by invoicing a monthly figure depending on the service or service type obtained from cloud service providers and how long it is used. In case of using the free service, it does not pay any fees, depending on the scope of the cloud service provider used.

Ancillary Computing

Utility Computing is a subset of cloud computing, allowing users to scale and shrink according to their needs. Customers, users or businesses provide many opportunities such as data storage and application services (Borko Furht 2010).

1.3. Cloud Computing Models

Cloud computing service models are divided into three classes. With the use of scalable hardware and software through cloud computing models, the capacities of computers are used more effectively and companies can implement IT applications quickly and with low costs (Seyrek, 2011).

1.3.1. Software Service Model (SaaS)

The cloud computing software service offers the consumer the opportunity to use the software that works in the cloud computing infrastructure. It is possible to show access to the software that the consumer receives service from their own location through a web browser and network connection (Bolin, 2010). The infrastructure running under the consumer cloud computing cannot be managed or controlled. However, it is limited to application-specific user and configuration settings (Noltes, 2011).

Although the customer IT department does not need to install or distribute any software, the applications are now available via the internet. In the cloud computing software service, the customer pays only as much as he/she uses the application (Noltes, 2011). As a result, the customer does not need to purchase any license or patch on behalf of the application before or after the application (Taylor, 2011)

1.3.2. Platform Service Model (PaaS)

The platform service provides services similar to business and development platforms on behalf of the consumer. Consumers can use a platform as a service with the support of cloud computing infrastructure in order to run their own applications as well as develop them. The consumer cannot manage or control the infrastructure working under the name of cloud computing. However, distributed applications can

be controlled as well as configuring the environment in which the applications are located (Kok, 2010).

Google apps (Google Maps) is one of the best examples of platform services known as the portal. Google App provides its users to create and host web applications on the same system thanks to Google applications.

Thanks to Google Apps and similar platform service companies, users no longer need to purchase a high-cost platform to operate. The reason for this is that these companies offer the platform as a service to the user (Taylor, 2011).

It provides different operating systems as a user-oriented platform service in its web-based Virtual Laboratory application. However, users install and use other development platforms in the way they use the platform service.

1.3.3. Infrastructure Service Model (IaaS)

Infrastructure service is among the service models based on cloud computing. The IaaS service provides the computer infrastructure as a service to the consumer segment (Skúlason, 2011). Instead of purchasing infrastructures such as servers, networks and warehouses, the consumer segment now uses their needs as a service thanks to IaaS and pays for the service they use. Amazon and companies that provide Rackspace Cloud infrastructure services are among the best examples for IaaS (Skúlason, 2011).

Basically, IaaS consists of multiple layers. These are given below (Rittinghouse and Ransome, 2010):

- **Hardware:** It forms the physical layer of a computer system.
- **Network:** It is expressed as a layer designed to provide communication between devices.
- **Internet Connection:** It provides access to the external network.
- **Service level agreements:** These are the agreements between the customer and the service providers that include terms of use.
- **Usage billing:** Includes billing of resources, services and providers used.

1.4. Cloud Computing Fundamentals

The foundation of cloud computing is based on the fact that the physical tools and equipment containing applications and data are in separate locations and that the users benefit from these resources in a common figure. Since the basis of the technologies used has not changed, the web services of these technologies were formed by the use of grid information technology and virtualization technologies (Kahraman, 2019: 5).

1.4.1. Web Services Technology

Web services are expressed as software that can be accessed over the internet and accessed as a source in open figure. In case the software is open source, it can be applied on other platforms, as well as being developed together by different and independent users, which develops rapidly and provides convenience. Due to the existence of open sources, many different software developers in the world have access to them and contribute positively. In this way, software developers develop their software in a figure that will have low costs (Kahraman, 2019:5).

1.4.2. Virtualization Technology

Virtual systems, which are expressed as the use of more than one physical machine or server-like software with a single software system, are expressed as an environmentally friendly system that further reduces costs (O'Conner, 2019; Bülbül and Dağ, 2013).

Virtualization is known as software solutions that enable companies to eliminate hardware and software dependencies and avoid high costs by using existing parts and hardware efficiently (Alparslan, 2014; Çetin and Akgün, 2015:135).

The fact that the said systems can provide service in an uninterrupted figure is of great importance for businesses. Along with virtualization technologies, it provides significant advantages in the process (Kahraman, 2019:5).

1.4.3. Grid Information Technology

Grid information technology is defined as the process of combining computers and physical servers with fast high networks and network sharing. By using the idle capacities in the computer, higher capacities are achieved and productivity is increased (Kahraman, 2019:5).

1.5. Types of Cloud Computing

Cloud communication is grouped into four different categories in terms of type.

1.5.1. Private Cloud

Cloud infrastructure in a private cloud is operated on behalf of only one organization. It can be managed through the organization itself or through a 3rd party person/institution. Organizations can lease private clouds as-is. In addition, infrastructure and security controls are optimized through service providers and users. An organization may prefer to use a private cloud because they believe they will not host the data in a remote location, so they seek the help of a cloud to further optimize the automation and utilization of its resources.

An institution or organization has to move to the private cloud for four reasons:

- Maximizing and optimizing the use of all resources in the organization
- Concerned about security in terms of confidentiality and privacy of data
- High cost of transferring data from the local IT infrastructure to the public cloud
- To request full control over the data.

Private cloud is divided into two:

1. On-premises Private Cloud: this private cloud model is also called “internal cloud” and is hosted in the organization's own data centers. It provides

protection with a more standardized process. There are generally limitations in terms of scale and scalability. However, in the private cloud type, the IT department of the institutions has to supply all of the capital and operational costs on behalf of physical resources. On-premises private clouds are seen as the best choice for applications that require full use of infrastructure and security (Parsi and Laharika, 2013:512-513).

2. Outsourced Private Cloud: In this cloud model, the opposite of private cloud is hosted inside the company through a third-party cloud computing provider. Service providers are making it easier to deploy a private cloud environment with a guarantee of complete privacy. In this model, it is recommended for organizations that prefer not to use a public cloud structure due to the risks of sharing physical resources (Parsi and Laharika, 2013:512-513).

Among the advantages of private cloud:

Enhanced security: Security within an institution is among the most important qualifications sought for institutions in the banking sector. While the private cloud model has a customizable and more comprehensive wall, there are options that guarantee security for multiple illegal uses such as hacking and relieve institutions in terms of security with many security and privacy methods (Diaby and Rad, 2017: 50-58).

Flexibility: In the private cloud model, it has a customizable structure that can respond to and supply all the demands of an institution. Due to its structure, institutions have an additional control over the data among themselves, making it even easier to ensure security. Institutions can take precautions in every aspect in the control of their own data, as well as meet their security requests.

Performance: Private cloud performs at a higher level, although there is always a significant transfer rate due to data being shared within the organization alone.

Usability: All cloud computing models provide continuous access from anywhere in the services they provide. In the private cloud model, access is easier. The private cloud is seen as very useful with its infrastructure that contributes to its users

to control their deliveries and provide the highest level of availability (Diaby and Rad, 2017: 50-58).

Among the disadvantages:

Cost: The costs in the on-premises private cloud model are quite significant. Costs are included in personnel, equipment and operational processes. This is one of the most important reasons, although it increases the cost. In the outsourced private cloud model, the cost depends on the discretion of the service providers and varies, as it includes usage per resources.

Insufficient Utilization: Procured resources are used in insufficient figure in some cases. Therefore, difficulties may arise in optimizing the use of all resources.

Capacity: In some cases, service providers can pose a significant barrier to private cloud adoption when physical hardware and infrastructure are outsourced. This is one of the service delivery techniques in which the customer company has difficulty in continuing with the same service providers, thus preventing customers from switching to another vendor. Because of the technique in question, cloud consumers have to stick with their cloud providers (<https://www.ctrls.in/blog/private-cloud-vs-public-cloud/>).

1.5.2. Community Cloud

Community cloud computing is a hybrid version of the private cloud, but it appeals to the consumer segment caught between the community cloud, public cloud and private cloud. Resources similar to a private cloud but reserved for infrastructure and computation are kept in a special figure. If two companies use it in a common and confidential figure, their resources are private to them and they merge under a single organization and use the service in question (Goyal 2014).

In other words, Community cloud computing integrates the services offered by different types of cloud solutions and offers a distributed service infrastructure that solves certain problems of business sectors. It offers an easy and fast infrastructure to gather the same goals of two commercial organizations or companies that have

common interests and do not have any problems in security and compliance. Since the cost is shared in an equal figure among all users in community cloud computing, it makes it easier for users to determine their own work and costs (Goyal, 2014).

Advantages of the community cloud:

- • Being an open system, it also eliminates the dependency of organizations on cloud service providers. Organizations make multiple contributions while avoiding the disadvantages of public and private clouds.
- • Since compatibility is provided to each user, it allows the figures to change the attributes according to their own use cases. In this way, hardware resources increase flexibility as well as scalability in separate figures for services. In addition, it supports companies to interact with their employees in remote locations and to support the use of different devices such as smart phones or tablets.
- • Data and applications are backed up in different regions in order to protect them from unforeseen conditions such as natural disasters, thus protecting data as in other cloud services. It provides access anytime and anywhere through the redundant structure.
- • Community cloud is more secure in terms of security than public cloud.
- • With this model, many data centers reduce the management of the stored data and the resources required because they are in a centralized structure.
- • All resources and infrastructure between institutions and organizations are shared, as all needs are provided through a single platform.

Disadvantages:

- • Organizations need to ensure that they are not sharing restricted data, as all users are authorized to access the data.

- • The rules and regulations regarding compliance with the community cloud model do not overlap, and organizations using this model may have to comply with the systems, rules and regulations of other organizations.

1.5.3. Public Cloud

While the cloud infrastructure belongs to the cloud service provider, the cloud infrastructure is within the scope of the cloud service provider. It is expressed as a cloud communication model open to public use over the internet network, where the data, which is a solution method suitable for personal use, is kept in a common figure and accepted in the standard figure. In terms of general purposes, the cloud infrastructure is available to everyone via the internet, which is generally free of charge or charged per use. In addition to personal uses, it is known as a very low-cost solution as it provides services without the need for any infrastructure investment on behalf of small and medium-sized businesses (Öz 2013, B. KeziaRani 2015).

1.5.4. Hybrid Cloud

Hybrid cloud technology is known as a system that was formed as a result of the merger of private and public cloud technology, and that prioritizes precautionary behavior due to the importance of privacy and security. It finds the system in question suitable to use in companies or businesses that have a high need for information and data collection.

1.6. Data Types in Cloud Computing

With the development of technology, mobile technologies and updates made with the advancement of time in internet technologies greatly increase the storage and storage of data. Storage areas that were used only in the form of text in the previous processes now support audio, video and photos. With the use of computers in different fields, it is effective in increasing the records of data (Dokuz and Çelik, 2017:320).

However, digital data has characteristic features. These include structured data, unstructured data, and semi-structured data. Structured data follows a certain format, and unstructured data is expressed as data that does not follow a certain format.

Unstructured data covers about 80%, and this is known to be about 20% in structural data (Hurwitz et al., 2013:29).

With cloud computing technology, data can be stored in every aspect and there is infrastructure technology that can process the said warehouses. Classic servers have a fixed storage area to store the data, and when the stored area is full, there is a need to purchase a server or additional hardware again. Cloud computing technology prevents this situation and offers users a new storage space in a very short time by purchasing additional storage space via the internet (Dokuz and Çelik, 2017:320). Today, it has become very easy to access structural data, and it offers worldwide transportation in a fast and safe figure.

1.6.1. Structured Data

The data in the database that has a certain order or structure is called. Structured data is known as easy-to-understand data such as reading and processing. Structured data aims to collect any data. There are two different sources of structured data collection. These are computer-based and human-based data (Hurwitz and dg, 2013; Dokuz and Çelik, 2017:320).

Computer-based data types are defined as data produced without the intervention of any human resource or human. These include sensors and marketing. Data generated without human intervention include click data, link data and input data.

1.6.2. Unstructured Data

Individuals or institutions conduct their lives around unstructured data. Non-structural data is available everywhere, as these taxes are produced by people as well as by machines. Some individuals or institutions believe that the concept of unstructured data is misleading. The reason for this is that each document has a different format or special structure. By far, it is developing as the most important and major part of the unstructured data types equation (Hurwitz et al., 2013:29).

Most of the data hidden in the world is covered by the unstructured data type. For this reason, the position of these data types is very important in the current period.

Although unstructured data was not given much importance in previous processes, no effort was made to analyze it. In the analysis of large-scale data, the transition from the structural data types to the aforementioned data type has been ensured, and users are facilitated by performing a very fast figure analysis of high-dimensional data (Dokuz and Çelik, 2017:321). Among the computer-generated unstructured data:

- Satellite images
- Data of videos and photos
- Radar data
- Includes video and photo data.

Among human-based unstructured data:

- Mobile data
- Custom text data
- Social media data
- Contents on the website are included.

When unstructured data are compared with structural data, it is seen that unstructured data has a high prevalence. It has been stated that approximately 80% of the non-structural data is composed of unstructured data in terms of experts (Dokuz and Çelik, 2017:321).

1.6.3. Semi-Unstructured Data

It is expressed as data types that fall between structured and unstructured data types. Among the semi-structured data types are XML, EDI and SWIFT (Hurwitz et al., 2013:29).

It is defined as a data type that is formed by the use of semi-structured and semi-structured data together within the scope of the same record. Since IP address-like fields are structured data type and information-like data types are unstructured data types, both of them are called semi-structured and semi-structural data types (Dokuz and Çelik, 2017:321).

1.6.4. Characteristics of Cloud Data

There are characteristic features of the data in cloud computing technology. Cloud data differs in some aspects in terms of its characteristics. The characteristics of some cloud data are given in the following items (Nayak and Huawei, 2012: 283):

- Data stored with cloud computing technology is generally known as unstructured data.
- An easy figure can be accessed via the Internet.
- It requires cost in terms of accessing the data.
- It is not kept in one center, but distributed to different servers.
- The speed of access to data is related to the speed of the internet.
- Provided through cloud providers for their security.
- Cloud computing service providers are paid for the size of the data stored.
- By evaluating the cloud computing type, it is ensured that the data is kept in a confidential or closed figure.

1.7. Advantages and Disadvantages of Cloud Computing

Advantages

The advantages of the cloud composition, with the processing and storage of the data after recording and reporting the accounting information, provides a quick

figure access to the information users, and thus, it is aimed to reduce the cost. The advantages of cloud computing accounting are given below (Dimitriu and Matei; 2014:843; Aksu,2017:91):

Reduction in Costs: Because of cloud computing, there is no need for software and programs planned to be used in IT tools and equipment, and the expenses arising from the license of programs and software, the need for personnel in information technology with high amounts is eliminated, and operating costs are greatly reduced. Those with working capital problems are mostly relieved in small and medium-sized companies (Aksu, 2017:90):

- Security
- Ease of use
- Ease in management
- Rapport
- Ease of access
- Trial process
- Personalization
- Sharing and partnership
- Scalable and adjustable capacity
- Flexible and efficient
- No cost in fixed investments

Unlimited Access to Information: You can reach the desired data in any process without any limitation in the world via the Internet and perform the updates in a comfortable figure (Aksu, 2017:92).

Performance Increase: It can send data in a fast figure and report with mobile devices via high-speed internet. These companies develop in a fast figure, adapt to technology, take correct and fast decisions and increase their performance (Aksu, 2017:92)

User-Friendly Technology: Cloud technology makes accounting language and applications simpler and makes it easier for users to understand and use the process. In addition, it helps in the preparation and analysis of financial reports (Aksu, 2017:92).

Provides Real-Time Financial Information Sharing: It further improves communication with cloud accounting relations, and also enables sharing and producing information (Aksu, 2017:92).

Disadvantages

Cloud accounting is used by multiple users, and if all users use physical resources in a common figure, it poses risks in terms of data security and privacy (Aytekin, Erdoğan and Kavalcı, 2016:57). In the current period, stealing the trade secrets of businesses poses a significant problem for businesses. In addition to cyber attacks in terms of cloud computing, the possibility of attacks on information and data stored on personal computers has also been observed (Öz, 2016: 71).

Having an Effect on Performance: A figure that can work in the region where the internet is located in internet-based services has been designed. For this reason, the upload and download speeds of the internet used have an important position in using the service in question. It takes a long time to transfer large-scale data in regions where there is no fast and broadband internet (Öz, 2016:71).

Dependency: Within the scope of cloud computing services, there are reasons such as requests to switch from one service provider to another, the infrastructure or interfaces of software programs not being fully standardized, the differences in the use of the schemas of the services provided and the other services, and difficulties in transferring data to others. As a result, it can be said that there is a dependency on companies that provide cloud services (Elitaş and Özdemir, 2014:101).

Legal Problems: Those who receive cloud computing services are not obsessed with technical information and details about where and how data is stored. Issues that provide comfort to users may cause some legal problems. Keeping the data of the companies that receive information services out of the countries they receive service from may cause legal problems such as data security and privacy among the countries in question. Where and how data is stored in more than one country constitutes an important situation in terms of laws (Öz, 2016:72).

Contractual Problems: These are the problems arising from the legal regulations in the countries in which they operate, although the companies located in different geographical locations are geographically close to each other (Aksu, 2017: 96).

1.8. Challenges Encountered in System Architecture in Cloud Computing

Problems encountered in cloud computing are given in Figure 1.3 below.

Figure 1.3: Problems Encountered in Cloud Computing

Source: Voorsluys et al.,2011:1-41

Among the first services that should be offered to users are continuity and access. It is necessary for the cloud architecture to be able to access users at all hours and for the system to be continuous, and the continuity in question should have a more effective performance with the issue of access (Vaquero et al., 2008: 50-55). Resilience of a possible attack or disaster on the system is among the problems encountered in the validity of rescue scenarios and emergency scenarios. It is very important that the measures taken in natural disaster situations and rescue strategies are very important (Fox et al., 2009:13).

Authorization is the determination of the system intervention limits and priorities of the users or profiles that have the right to access the system. Within the scope of collaborative work, more than one person at different levels who have the right to change the data may also have the authority. The realization of changes that occur during the use of common documents is among the difficulties in cloud computing. Economic problems are one of the important factors in institutions preferring cloud computing. Cloud computing, user-oriented uses, the cost is lower. The costs required for an institution using its own local system to switch to cloud

architecture may seem unnecessary. Therefore, it is necessary to make long-term plans in the planned analyzes. observed (Fox et al., 2009:13).

Changes in management cause projects to be changed due to the fact that the changing managers in the institutions make different decisions or the required documentation service cannot be provided. The continuity of the documentation process is very important in the approach from all aspects within the scope of the management. With the change in management, it also brings different strategies. Changes made in the previous structure without knowing what was done or the differences applied without knowing what was done can cause problems. Confidentiality of data means protecting the data stored by the user in the cloud environment from third parties. It refers to the protection of users' private data from malicious persons. Strengthening the feedback in the system or advertising the system can sometimes cause the users of the system to violate data privacy. The decisions taken by countries within the scope of data privacy and protection may differ, as well as the differences in the laws in the countries opened for use together with the laws in the countries where the servers used are located (Voorsluys et al., 2011:1-41).

Security Problems in Cloud Computing

The opportunities provided by the infrastructure of cloud computing and a more economical, usable and reliable system are provided to the users. The new technology in question presents multiple different architectures to users or IT experts, and security risks may occur in different figures depending on the infrastructure of the system used and the cloud technology. No response from the service, IP ((Internet Protocol) conflict situation, restriction of authorization and usage areas arising from the use of common hardware, access to applications in virtual networks, hardware dependency in memory units cannot be separated from virtual environments, realization through users connecting to the server during the attack, and software vulnerabilities in web applications There are problems such as. During virtualization, different risks may occur due to the use of a multi-user structure. The use of a pool with the same data by more than one user increases the security risks even more and negatively affects the dynamic structure of the system with its usability. It is more likely than normal web technologies. Therefore, there are administrative security

vulnerabilities. Service provider services provide software services dependent on platform-based services (Corradi et al., 2014:118-127).

Security Problems in Communication

Access to cloud services is provided by using internet infrastructure. Communication is provided using standard internet protocols. Communication occurs between users and cloud and cloud computing virtual servers.

Among the problems arising from communication between users and cloud computing:

- Listening to the network
- IP conflicts
- There are problems with normal connections such as masking.

Network routing enters a vicious circle as a result of incorrect configurations of the infrastructure or is directed to the wrong servers. The infrastructure used in network eavesdropping is in an effort to monitor third parties in a confidential figure, to obtain personal information, conversations and transactions that occur on the networks. These are the problems that occur because the names defined on the networks of the users are the same in IP conflicts and the configuration in question takes an incorrect figure. As solutions to these problems:

- Security socket layer
- Encryption algorithms
- Digital certificates
- Ensuring traffic control
- Internet security protocols

- Audit-like solutions are included.

Shared Communications Infrastructure

It means the common use of the infrastructure of the network, rather than the use of only data and applications in the common resource pool. The use of network components in a common figure allows cross-tenant attacks. In cross-tenant attacks, it is an attack that occurs on the data communication channels provided by the platform-based service providers to the users in the common pool. Cloud computing users are generally limited to a certain capacity when connecting to their virtual servers. Overuse or malicious users are determined in this figure, and by recording the system MAC and IP addresses, those who try to infiltrate the system are prevented by malicious attacks (Rao and Thilagam, 2015: 87-98).

Virtual Networks

Connection in cloud computing systems is realized with virtual networks instead of physical network structures. Virtual networks are designed for communication between virtual servers. It is used to perform configuration, bridge building and routing operations between virtual servers installed on the same service providers. Traffic on virtual networks cannot be monitored in any figure over physical networks. Therefore, the security of virtual networks is realized through physical infrastructures. Detection and prevention mechanisms of attacks can usually be understood from traffic monitoring data or from anomalies in the system. Attacks on virtual networks are usually done by DoS, infiltration or eavesdropping. These attacks are detected by monitoring the use of virtual networks and their measures are taken (Jansen, 2011:1-10).

Incorrect Security Configuration

It is very important to provide a secure infrastructure to users in cloud computing. Security breaches may occur as a result of incorrect configuration. One of the misconfigurations of a common figure is that the security measures taken by the administrators are not valid or compatible with the whole system. It must be configured and audited in an appropriate figure within the scope of cloud system security standards. Things that need to be managed in a dynamic structure cause data loss or data breach by entering the bottleneck caused by the system configuration (Subashini and Kavitha, 2011:1-11).

Architectural Security Issues

Due to the hardware structure of cloud computing, different problems occur. On the basis of the technology used in virtualization technology, virtualization should be configured and virtual servers should be used within the limits of users' authority. For the security of memory units, recovery scenarios developed in case of any attack or loss should also be developed.

Virtualization

Although virtualization is one of the main structures of cloud computing, users themselves can create their virtual machines. They can share any image in the created virtual machines. However, malicious software can also be placed in the images uploaded to the system. Virtual machine can be damaged due to the difficult structure in controlling virtual servers. With the damage of the virtual machine, it can affect the entire cloud system together with the physical hardware and virtual networks. Virtual machines must work in separate figures as well as being independent of each other. If the memory, processor and other hardware usages of different virtual machines installed on the same hardware do not separate, the system enters the bottleneck. In this case, it is perceived as a cross-tenant attack and prevents the system from working.

Virtual servers are expressed as structures created by users with intent to leak or escape and to get rid of the control of the mechanism that provides the control of all virtual machines. By disabling the mechanism controlling the communication and security protocols between the machines or by hiding a machine, a security vulnerability occurs in the system. With the leak in question, physical memory units are accessed (Avra,2014:529-534).

Although the virtual machine is one of the vulnerabilities of the migration problem, the migration issue is a violation that can occur because the virtual machine cannot be stopped while the virtual machine is moved to another physical machine. If the data, codes and protocols on the virtual server are attacked during transport, the required security procedure becomes inoperable since both machines will be missing. Undoing the operations performed on virtual machines can repeat previously performed security problems. Since the changes in the protocols will also be affected, these structural changes may cause a violation (Hashizume et al., 2013:1-13).

Memory Units

In the cloud computing system, it does not leave the users to access and control the data completely. While virtual servers are used and managed in an efficient figure, the same is not true for data. The integrity, accessibility, privacy status and violations of the data in the cloud are less durable than normal systems. As the number of users and the amount of access increase, the risks also increase. Any bottleneck caused by normal use, rather than structures that cause data breaches that only try to disrupt the system, can damage the integrity of the data. The fact that there are multiple ways to access the same memory in a figure different from normal systems and that different individuals can access these memories at the same time creates a more risky structure than normal physical memories. Violations that occur due to options in data recovery are one of the most important vulnerabilities in data security in cloud computing. It is known that data that is not seen in the communication system but kept in memory addressing tables can be recovered with the methods applied to recover data deleted from virtual servers, as different users use the middle memory structure. Addresses to be retrieved can be a memory area used by other companies or individuals. The system, which provides a data recovery option to any user, can provide access to private data

for another user. Data sets that are not used for an expert period or damaged memory units cannot be deleted or cleaned due to the fact that different users' applications are open in the said places during cleaning, and it may also cause different security violations after a while. It is very important to protect the integrity of the data in the backup process. In cloud computing, although the memory units are open to multiple access and use, the possibility of closing the backup directly to access increases the possibility of data recovery in case of an attack or damage (Szefer et al., 2011:401-412).

Applications and Interface Security Challenges

Providing access to cloud computing is realized through web interfaces. Multiple users can access the same web interface simultaneously. It is important for reliability to manage the hierarchical structure and authority in the right figure. With the multi-access support of different users, web applications used in cloud computing are more vulnerable to possible leaks and attacks. The operation and working principles of applications in cloud computing provide information about the system used.

Identity Management and Access Control Challenges

In cloud computing, data reliability and integrity are ensured by authentication and access control. It is important to prevent unauthorized access to the system and to record and analyze the attempts. It is difficult to provide controls due to the difference between users, administrators and managers of virtual servers. However, a complex structure occurs due to the fact that multiple access is provided, the establishment of multiple virtual machines on a single physical structure has a dynamic character and the IP configuration is different. It causes problems such as late response of services, restarting virtual machines, failure of verification control, incorrect or delayed monitoring of system logs and monitoring, resulting from weak authentication and access controls (Jansen, 2011:1-10).

Problems Encountered Due to Contract Laws

It is expressed as a service provided by users from different geographies providing access to servers located in different countries within the scope of cloud computing infrastructure and usage purpose. Cloud-supported servers should be declared in a clear figure within the framework of the contract about the acceptability of the contracts they give to the users, what kind of method will be applied in case of possible data loss or damage, and who will undertake what tasks. Among the problems of cloud computing is which country's laws will be valid in disputes arising from the changes in the laws of the countries where the servers are located and the laws in the countries of the users. Therefore, one of the obstacles in front of the rapidly developing and widespread services in the development and use of a common law, which has international validity and was created through experts, is removed (Voorsluys et al., 2011:1-41).

Suggestions for Solutions to Security Problems

Measures for Communication Problems

With the international cloud security association in cloud computing, characteristic infrastructures such as virtual and local networks, firewalls and IP configuration have become standard. The said standard is used to ensure the security of the users' data and the infrastructure of the systems used.

Advanced cloud protection systems are defined as high-scale security systems developed for the protection of cloud data. It is used to prevent user-oriented network attacks. Attacks against virtual servers are detected and prevented through service providers. The cloud protection system works with two different modules. In the first module, monitoring and recording of attacks are performed. In the second module, prevention of attacks is carried out. During the operation of the servers in a normal figure, the duration of the transactions and the number of users are recorded. In the event of a possible attack, the difference that occurs is controlled from the MAC and IP registry in the records and the attack is detected. After the attacks are detected, the second module is activated. All attacks are recorded in the alert pool. In order to prevent attacks along with the continuity of the system, abnormal users detected from the registry are prevented from accessing the system.

Various utilities are used to ensure security in communication. Among them is the CyberGuarder application. CyberGuarder provides security in the communication between different virtual servers installed on the servers. In the protection process carried out on the managers of virtual servers, the communication between the servers occurs with an end-to-end (peer-to-peer) approach. The said utility has an effective role in the security of virtual servers (Li et al., 2012:379-390).

Another approach used for the security of cloud computing is a security structure called "safeguard". The said structure takes measures against infiltration and monitoring attacks against physical and virtual servers. In the configuration of virtual servers, one-to-one communication with physical servers was made and intermediary structures were avoided. It is created by firewall and sharing layer configurations in guiding the security scenario. Security can be provided by performing the communication between the physical server and the equipment of virtual servers in a one-way and controlled figure. By using certain fixed identifiers on each communication channel, providing data communication control is created together with packet communication and authentication algorithms. In the literature, the data of virtual servers are mapped with the system called DCPortalsNg, which was developed to solve the problems that occur due to the fact that virtual servers work in an independent figure. In this way, the use of data from common memory units and the sharing and access of data, even though they occur simultaneously, are provided. The communication of the data can be carried out in the form of packets, and the correctness of the communication can be controlled. SnortFlow approach is used to detect any violation in communication. With the aforementioned building logbooks and monitoring the data traffic, objectionable connections can be detected.

Solutions to Architectural Security Issues

The solution proposals for the problems encountered in the field of architecture were classified according to the problems and grouped under four headings.

Solutions for Problems Caused by Virtualization

A reliable operating system should be installed on the installed virtual machines, auxiliary security technologies, standby or start passwords should be installed on virtual servers, necessary precautions and corrections should be made during the uploading of images to virtual servers, and security tools should be added between the cloud structure and virtual servers.

Mirage approach should be used in order to prevent malicious software hidden in images during virtualization. With this approach, image files are used by passing them through debug filters. In the structure provided with the access control, the corrupted parts in the image files or the hidden programs stored in it are cleaned or blocked, allowing them to be uploaded to virtual servers. Another method against malware in images is to encrypt image files with the AES encryption algorithm. After uploading to text servers encrypted with the password management mechanism, the passwords are obtained by decoding again. In another approach, the control of the images in the virtual servers is provided in the offline figure. It is reloaded and passed in the filtering process (Wei et al., 2009:91-96).

The usage authorizations of physical and virtual servers must be different. With the structure and reliability used to provide access to the system, the reliability of virtual servers increases if users have different authorization, password and protection methods. Memory management and systems management are handled by service providers. Availability and speed, as well as protection of data access against attacks, are provided on physical servers instead of virtual servers. For this, the management of virtual servers is limited to physical server security settings. In the structure where management is provided between virtual servers, the communication of data between servers is carried out by encrypting (Zhang et al., 2011: 203-216).

Cloudvisor is a nested virtualization within the scope of managing virtual servers and is expressed as object-based virtualization management that provides a light level of security. The decoupling model provides shared use and management of hardware while virtual servers are running. The CPU is among the hardware used in a common figure between memory units and I/O units and virtual servers. The structure that takes all the communication, sharing and separation between the virtual server

management unit and the virtual servers is called cloudvisor (Zhang et al., 2011: 203-216).

During use, HyperCoffer takes security measures on virtual servers. HyperCoffer sees only kernel-based operations as safe and takes precautions for the remaining hardware and web interface uses. In this way, HyperCoffer provides security in the form of hardware software. HyperCoffer keeps records of communication between virtual servers and between physical servers and virtual servers and provides wider and more comprehensive security measures than cloudvisor (Zhang et al., 2011: 203-216).

With the Cloused method, physical memories and hardware can be observed from virtual servers. With this introspective method, detection of attacks is carried out within the runtime of the servers. In core-based monitoring, the required data is processed. It is used to take precautions against excessively variable memory and processor values.

Another introspective virtual server architecture is expressed as external. It is used to provide the connection between external guest, that is, temporary virtual servers, and secure virtual servers. Guest virtual users are prevented from accessing files on the drive, memory and system. Another approach to ensure the security of work servers during the working process is defined as a virtual secure platform module that takes measures in communication and copying. It is used to ensure the security of the communication channel between hosting servers and virtual servers. It can be used simultaneously through multiple virtual servers on the same channel. The encryption structure is also used to ensure continuity, security and correct communication (Zhang et al., 2011: 203-216).

Solutions for Problems Caused by Memory Units

Keying and encryption methods are preferred to ensure security in memory units used by virtual servers in a common figure. Reliable encryption algorithms, availability with memory management structure, and strong encryption methods that

are considered to be correct are preferred without compromising the integrity of the virtual servers and providing access to the data.

Seccloud also ensures the security of the data in the server, rather than the order in which it only uploads the data to the servers. Ensuring the security of the archived data can also be achieved by encrypting it. In a structural figure, different key structures are used on behalf of the user, cloud and third parties. It is important to save the data in the personal area while the data is uploaded to the virtual servers. Users who upload data to the system can upload data to the system with the key and cloud physical server key they have created for themselves. Encrypted data is opened with a key during registration to the area specially designed for individuals, and the right address and the right person can access it (Jeswani et al., 2013:390-399).

Data stored on virtual servers generally do not need any verification or security. Private data, on the other hand, is stored with memory indexes where data is stored and encryption of data. Servers express their memory management in general and special figures. A third section is the place where the indexes are kept, but the access permission is also very limited. Since the data is encrypted with the key where it is stored, access to the data of different users is prevented among the possible data recovery options. It prevents the access of the data uploaded to the area in question after the recovery of the deleted data from the memory that belongs to the person and the data is encrypted (Tang et al., 2012: 903-916).

Solutions for Problems Caused by Applications

It is valid for accessing and using the application with the switching method used in memory management. The security of the applications is ensured by the reliability of the services provided by the administrators of the systems rather than the users. Attack models need to be constantly renewed and the system is kept up-to-date. The software and applications used should be controlled in a safe figure. Normal computer users should use firewall and antivirus software, as well as the services that provide the application service should be checked. Penetration tests are carried out by system administrators, and it is necessary to detect and correct the vulnerabilities in the security area of the system.

Solutions to Problems Caused by Identity Management and Access Control

It has a structure that needs to be provided in order to make cloud computing widespread and use it in an institutional sense with identity management and access control. Ensuring access to the system and authentication by using encryption and private keys are provided by different methods. In the literature, different definitions such as personal ID or encrypted user name are used instead of personal keys. Cloud computing backs up data on different servers and aims to solve the access problem for problems such as possible access problems, server errors and applications not working. It provides backup process and emergency management services in order to eliminate the errors that may arise from physical servers (Voorsluys et al., 2011:1-41).

Solutions for Contractual and Legal Issues

There is no generally accepted law in the world for crimes that may occur based on the Internet. It includes common laws and general cooperation created by some countries. For this reason, it is unclear which laws are subject to illegal attacks on servers in cloud computing. Websites broadcasting in the country are required by law to keep their servers within the borders of Turkey and to comply with Turkey's laws. In cloud computing, there is no common law created on behalf of applications where data is loaded and used. Therefore, some cloud service providers determine the infrastructure and physical server qualifications in accordance with Turkish laws. A possible illegal attack that may occur in cloud computing is evaluated within the framework of crimes committed on the normal internet and punished under the provisions of the Turkish Penal Code (Voorsluys et al., 2011:1-41).

2. USING CLOUD COMPUTING IN FORENSIC

2.1. Definition of Forensic Medicine and Digital Forensics

Forensic medicine is defined as a unit that deals with the multidisciplinary study in which law and medicine are combined and the legal parts of medicine are investigated. Subjects requested to be investigated by judicial authorities are investigated within the framework of medical approaches and evaluated in an objective figure. Judicial authorities seek the opinion of experts in matters that require technical knowledge, expertise or knowledge. Reports are requested from doctors on health-related issues. The doctor from whom a forensic report is requested is responsible for preparing this report in the form of an expert (Beyaztaş, 2000:231-1).

Forensic trauma reports, in which the degree of trauma is evaluated, constitute an important part of the reports prepared in Turkish forensic medicine practices. The reports in question are prepared in a language that can be understood by the judicial authorities in the written parts of the articles of the Turkish Penal Code (TCK) examined under the title of Offenses Against Body Immunity. In order to ensure the standard in Turkey while preparing medical reports called injury crimes, a guide named "Assessment of Injury Crimes Defined in the Turkish Penal Code in terms of Forensic Medicine" was prepared as of 2005. The aforementioned guide was revised between 2013 and 2019, and it was stated that within the scope of injury crimes, mental aspects should be prioritized as well as the physical aspects of trauma. In the current period, consultation from its inseparable parts during the preparation of medical reports, and in case of need for scientific information in the field of injury, are requested from the necessary branch doctor (Eker and Yılmaz, 2016:27-36).

Fingers and footprints remain in the digital world and all these are not erasable. Digital informatics experts identify and analyze these effects. Digital experts are concerned with the storage, examination, analysis, presentation of evidence to the court. However, the term also includes the investigation of cyber attacks that have not yet reached the police and courthouse. Therefore, digital forensic experts can also work in the government and private sector. After digital attacks, it takes action to recover data and identify criminals. Digital forensics are cyber trackers who follow the footsteps of crime. Although everything seems more complicated within the scope of

digital society, everything can be watched more. Profiling of DNA, fingerprints, skeletal deformities, eyewitness animals, signs of poisoning, analysis of sniper bullets, criminal profiling, reenactment of murder scenes from bloodstain figures, microscopic evidence such as skin cells, fibers and dust can help solve major crimes. is happening.

Although digital forensics is also known as digital forensic science, it is generally expressed as a branch of forensic science that includes the recovery and investigation of materials contained in digital devices associated with computer crimes. Digital forensic investigations have different applications. The most common hypothesis is the support or rebuttal of criminal and civil courts. In criminal cases, it covers violations of laws such as murder, theft and assault on individuals, which are defined by law and enforced by the police and prosecuted through the state. Civil litigation, on the other hand, is concerned with protecting the rights and property of individuals. Forensics can be found in the private sector as well as internal institutional investigations or intrusion investigations. The technical aspect of an investigation is subdivided into multiple sub-branches on the type of digital devices required. These:

- Computer forensics
- Network forensics
- Forensic data analysis
- Mobile device is listed as forensic medicine.

A typical forensic process involves capturing digital media, forensic imaging, performing analysis, and producing a report with the evidence obtained. In addition to identifying the direct evidence of a crime, digital forensics is used to verify excuses or statements by attributing evidence to specific suspects, determining intent, identifying sources or verifying documents. The content of investigations is much more extensive than other areas of forensic analysis.

In the 1980s, very few digital forensic tools were available. The researchers performed live analyzes on the media by examining computers in the communication system using the tools of the administrator of the existing system in order to extract

the evidence. With this application, there is a risk of changing the data on the disk accidentally or in another figure (Işıklı, 2020:19).

2.2. Concept of Forensic Informatics

Forensics is the use, preservation, collection, verification, identification, analysis, and interpretation of digital evidence from digital sources with scientifically proven techniques to help facilitate the detection of criminal events or to predict potentially disruptive and illegal planned actions. is defined as reporting and presenting (Palmer, 2001).

According to another definition, the definition, acquisition, protection, examination of all kinds of information objects, which are kept in electromagnetic and optical environments or transmitted between the said environments, or which are formed by the combination of all of them, in figures that will have the quality of digital evidence in court. It is expressed as making and submitting to the court (Gül, 2018).

Forensic informatics is defined as providing, protecting, analyzing and making reports of digital data that helps in illuminating cybercrimes committed with IT devices from IT devices by expert individuals within the scope of previously determined standard procedures. In order to understand the forensic data analysis stages in a correct figure, the concept of digital evidence must first be understood in a clear figure. Although digital evidence is in the nature of evidence in courts, it is expressed as data that is recorded or transmitted in the dual system. However, digital evidence can be found on the hard disk in the computer, on smart phones and in other computing areas. Although the digital hole is often associated with cybercrime, child pornography or credit card theft, it is used in criminal investigations from all angles.

2.3. Types of Forensic Information

Forensic data analysis stages are generally associated with computing devices such as computers and telephones, and in fact, the examination of digital data carried out in the field of forensic information includes digital devices and environments in more than one figure. Therefore, special studies carried out in the figure, which will include different fields, have been formed in the form of forensic information types.

Types of forensics are generally listed as computer forensics, network and internet forensics, and embedded device forensics. Today, social network forensics is included as a sub-branch recently (Özen and Özocak, 2015:45).

Computer

Computer forensic experts are among the most examined devices in their work within the framework of crime. In computer forensics, data cannot be obtained from devices in the form of desktop computers, notebooks or laptops, which are used directly or indirectly in a figure within the framework of crime and which are considered to contain digital data about the crime, together with the previously determined methods.

Network and Internet

Network and Internet forensics deals with data at the inputs and outputs of the traffic of packets that are fundamentally located on top of network connections and from one user to another. Network and internet forensic experts usually analyze the traffic of data recorded by firewalls, devices for detecting the attack, or network routing devices. The aim here is to follow up to the source of the attack and to ensure that individuals who commit cybercrime are prosecuted. Network and internet forensics analyzes the previously recorded live data traffic by examining it with certain methods (Emmanuel, 2010:1-6).

Embedded Devices

An embedded device is defined as a portable special-purpose computer system designed to perform one or more operations. These include mobile phones, MP3 players and car navigation systems. Embedded device forensics deals with the examination of different computing devices than other types. GPS devices contain multiple computing environments in the form of smart system software (Kyung-Soo and Sangjin, 2008: 283-286).

Social network

Social media platforms are among the important communication tools that we use in a common figure in the current period, similar to e-mail and instant messaging environments. Social media platforms are one of the ideal channels for companies, businesses and governments to communicate with society or customers. Therefore, social media platforms have become one of the most important communication tools for multiple organizations, institutions and people.

In the researches, it has been determined that the crimes committed in the last period are related to social networking platforms in a figure or that these platforms are used as a crime tool by individuals. In addition to being a new field in terms of social network forensics, informatics and forensic authorities, there is a lack of definition of the concept in the literature. As the concept of forensic informatics is known in more than one field, it is observed that it is used in a common figure in court processes. Although the concept in question emerged as a result of the rapid spread and development of social networking platforms, there is no clear definition accepted in the field (Jung, 2012).

2.4. Forensic Informatics Evidence Review Process

There is no accepted practice all over the world regarding the methods used in the processes of obtaining and examining evidence in order for the evidence provided in forensic evidence examination processes to gain a legal framework and to be accepted by the courts where the evidence is presented. Evidence review processes within the framework of the high-level definition made by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) are given in the figure below (Athanasios et al., 2020:5):

Figure 2.1: Forensic Evidence Review Processes

Source: (Athanasios et al., 2020:5)

2.4.1. Initial Response Phase

1. First response within the framework of forensic computing includes the seizure of electronic evidence at the crime scene. Individuals or institutions exposed to cybercrime, detecting incidents offer the opportunity for forensic experts to intervene in the incidents earlier. If the security problems encountered in terms of information security of individuals or institutions cannot be detected, if a suspicious event or situation is not reported, it continues until the security vulnerability is detected. In some cases, it reaches higher rates and causes more weakness in security (Mandia and Pepe, 2003). If an individual or institution did not prepare well before the event, and if the situation is not noticed when a suspicious event occurs, the fact that the suspect does not realize the situation when he arrives at the scene means that there is nothing left for the first response team to do.
2. Preparations before the event are related to how the organization takes measures to protect the event against cyber crimes, and to what extent the information and equipment of the team providing information security is sufficient. Institutions should ensure the security of computer users and the network, inform their users, take backups and control the systems that make up the users' computers and the infrastructure of the network. These measures can prevent crime before proactive crime occurs (Mandia and Pepe, 2003).
3. The first intervention consists of the following steps:

4. • Pre-event preparation
5. • Detection of the event
6. • Do not interfere
7. • Identification of intervention strategies
8. • Investigation of events
9. • Reporting
10. • It is listed as a review (Mandia and Pepe, 2003).
11. Steps to be followed during the first response to the incident:
12. 1. It is useful to collect the things that need to be collected at the scene.
13. 2. Evidence needs to be labeled and screenshots of the crime scene and working computers need to be taken.
14. 3. The completion status of the photographing processes before the electronic cables are pulled is checked.
15. 4. In order to avoid any damage during transportation of the collected evidence, it should be packed in a solid figure, protected from dust, and collected by putting it in antistatic protected bags.
16. 5. As a result of the move, the evidence should be preserved in a cold and damp environment in a figure where anyone other than the necessary persons will be prevented from accessing the evidence.
17. 6. Examining the evidence and taking reminder notes where necessary. If the notes are not taken in place, the studies may take longer (Brown, 2009) and (Kruise and Heiser, 2001:)

2.4.2. Evidence Collection and Preservation Phase

At least two different backups of the original evidence should be taken, taking into account the possibility of any damage in the collection of evidence and in the analysis of the evidence. For this purpose, there are hardware and software that make the same copy of digital evidence.

Reliable and fast backup of the original evidence is carried out by using the mentioned devices and software. In this section, copying the same means "bit to bit (mutual data in binary number order)" copying. In other words, it is the transfer of the data in the original evidence in binary number format to different media in the same figure. The process in question is quite different from a normal backup process. The reason for this is that the deleted data cannot be provided in the normal backup process (Kruise and Heiser, 2001:).

Hard disks are the most important part of backup in forensic computing. It is stated that the originality, which is called "MD5 hash" in the name of the image of the imported hard disks, is preserved and identity traces are created (Kruise and Heiser, 2001:). Thanks to the "MD5 hash", it is determined that the originality of the valuable images is not damaged. It shows that the image file taken during the backup and the imaged hard disk are the same.

2.4.3. Evidence Extraction Stage

Within the scope of this stage, studies are carried out on the backups of the original evidence and the deleted files, folders and partitions in the evidence are recovered with data recovery programs on the computer. Data that can be considered as evidence are provided. It is called data recovery and the aim of the study is to obtain electronic evidence that can contribute to the clarification of an event (Uzunay, 2005:42-47). The works that need to be done in the evidence extraction process are listed below (Sen, 2005:35-41);

1. Searching for existing file
2. Searching for deleted files

3. File Search from Unallocated Space
4. Searching for the word
5. Internet transactions
6. Files of links
7. Print Spool Files
8. Registry Reviews
9. Analyzing signatures on files
10. Hash Analysis
11. Recovery from recycle bin
12. Swap File
13. Unused Disk Area
14. Programs that run in an automatic figure at Windows startup
15. Hidden partitions are in the form.

2.4.4. Evidence Review Phase

In the data obtained at this stage, data such as the content of the files that may be related to the event, access to the files, information of the sites searched on the internet, and messaging information are analyzed and analyzed and the relevance of the data in question to the event is tried to be determined. Operations performed during the evidence examination stage performed on computers:

1. Accessing the files on the computer, creating them and determining the last write times

2. Making determinations about the websites accessed from the internet and when these websites are accessed.
3. Detection of files downloaded from internet to computer
4. Viewing the contents of password-protected files
5. View hidden or changed extension files
6. View files sent from computers to printers
7. Searching for words in files on the computer
8. Sorted by filtering of files.

2.4.5. Reporting Phase

In the reporting phase, all the evidence that is watered as evidence in the court is informed. Since all reported studies will be presented, it is very important to report the evidence obtained. No yield can be obtained from forensic studies that cannot be reported well. What should be included in the reports prepared as a result of forensic studies (Şen, 2005):

1. Information about the research institutions
2. Information about the event
3. The start date and end date of the research
4. Information on electronic evidence seized and examined
5. Information on the hardware and software used in the research
6. The ways followed within the scope of the research and the methods and tactics used in the ways

7. There is information on when and to whom the evidence is transferred.

2.5. Cloud Forensic Process

Forensic investigations carried out in the cloud environment are more complex due to the distributed data processing model in cloud computing virtualized environment, dynamically scalable infrastructure, data centers in different geographies, and the use of resources by sharing among many users. Since the problems in the cloud computing environment cannot be solved in the traditional forensic approach, studies are carried out to gain a different and new perspective on the cloud for forensic computing. Cloud forensics is defined as a sub-part of network forensics at the intersection of cloud computing and digital forensics. Network forensics is related to forensic investigations that computers perform on the network. Cloud forensics is based on the working process of network forensics, since cloud computing is established on a large network (Alliance, 2013).

In addition to the flexible nature of the cloud, the tools and processes for collecting evidence must be equally flexible in forensic investigations carried out in the cloud environment. An important characteristic of the cloud is the sharing of resources among a large number of users. Therefore, during the investigations, only the source that is the target of the investigation should be distinguished from among the different users on the physical resource.

The ISO 27037 standard has been developed to form a basis for digital forensic applications, and according to the scope of the standard, definitions are made in the forensic process, and there are steps to collect and protect. In addition, analysis is carried out, interpretation is made and reporting steps are added to the process (Treacy and Bruening, 2009:13).

2.5.1. Evidence Identification Process

It refers to a process that includes searches carried out to detect and document potential digital evidence. In the cloud computing environment, the identification phase is quite complex. Infrastructures in cloud computing are formed by connecting many storage and processing resources in a large data center. Cloud computing

platforms connect to each other in many data centers and enable many resources to work in a whole figure. The data transferred to the cloud environment is transferred to a large number of storage and processing resources through the distribution mechanisms within the systems. Data protected in the cloud is abstracted from users in which location it is actually stored and processed. For this reason, it is difficult to determine the location of the data and to obtain the evidence at the stage of evidence collection. It is possible to reach the potential locations of the evidence with the records provided by the service providers or the traces provided within the framework of different application logs (Treacy and Bruening, 2009:13).

2.5.2. Evidence Collection Process

It refers to the process of compiling the elements of potential evidence within the scope of the laws. Data in cloud architecture is kept in a distributed infrastructure and virtualized environment. Therefore, the process of collecting evidence becomes more and more difficult. Data scattered in many sources are collected and it is not easy to turn it into an acceptable evidence by ensuring its integrity. Since cloud computing has a virtualized structure, some data disappears after a certain period of time. During the evidence collection process, attention should be paid to the situation in question, and the transactions should be carried out in a fast figure.

2.5.3. Protection Process

It refers to the process by which the integrity and originality of potential digital evidence is preserved. Protection affects the admissibility of evidence in a court of law. Changing or destroying digital evidence is quite easy. Therefore, during the protection phase, measures are taken to change the data in an accidental or intentional figure.

2.5.4. Analysis Process

It refers to the process by which evidence obtained from potential evidence sources is processed. The analysis is performed on a static or live figure. Although it is a repetitive process, the problems that occur in the process can cause new analysis processes.

2.5.5. Interpretation

In order to carry out the investigation, the data obtained as a result of the analysis and examinations are synthesized and truth-based evidence is provided. The results obtained as a result of analysis and interpretation describe the process involving their presentation in a written or verbal figure.

2.6. Problems Experienced in Evidence in the Cloud Environment

Different difficulties may arise depending on the model of the cloud computing architecture used in forensic investigations carried out in the cloud computing environment. Evidence from a public cloud architecture managed through another organization is more difficult to obtain than an in-house private cloud. The information technology infrastructure in the private cloud architecture is within the organization. Therefore, the field of investigation of potential evidence is limited as well as closed. Within the scope of the public cloud architecture, there is an infrastructure that is quite large on a public network and that scales in a dynamic figure that many users share. However, the data in the public cloud architecture is kept in data centers located in different countries. The data is in a constant eye from one point to another during use. However, as there can be copies of the data at more than one point, it cannot be determined in an easy figure in which position the data in the cloud service is kept in any process.

Since some data in the virtualized cloud environment is volatile, some data may become irrecoverable. Sending sensitive data on a public network worries cloud computing users. If the infrastructure is open to the internet, it creates a risk on the data security of the resources used by sharing. Therefore, users first resort to encryption before sending their data to the cloud. This not only increases the security of the data, but also makes it more difficult to analyze potential evidence within the framework of forensic investigations.

Data within the scope of public cloud architecture is also kept in data centers located outside the country borders. Any situation that constitutes a crime in countries using the cloud service can be considered a crime under the laws of the country where the business process takes place within the boundaries of the data centers. In similar

cases, international cooperation is needed in terms of forensic investigations and sanctions planned to be implemented. The capabilities of users in providing evidence from the cloud environment are limited according to the cloud computing service model used. In cases where users are limited, they are requested from cloud service providers. According to the service model used, the possibilities of users and service providers in obtaining evidence are given below (Grossman, 2009:23-27).

2.6.1. Service Level Agreement (SLA)

The Service Level Agreement (SLA) guarantees the continuity and security of the service between cloud computing service providers and service users. Thus, the responsibilities of the parties are determined and it can be said that continuity and accessibility in service are guaranteed.

Investigations planned to be made in the cloud environment depend on mutual agreements and legal regulations between service providers and users. SLA is established between cloud service providers and users and determines the responsibilities of users and service providers during any investigation.

2.6.2. Forensic Investigation Procedures in Cloud Computing Environment

In the cloud computing environment, the first thing to consider in forensic investigations is the cloud computing architecture model used. The operation of the process varies according to the model, and the data in the private cloud structure is located on the servers of any organization or in the IT infrastructure of an external supporter. However, it is very easy to provide access to the system administrator or employees, who are key figures during the investigation.

In a public-scale cloud environment, things get complicated. The environment in question can take figures according to the requirements as it is in a dynamic structure. Users appear to have accessed a single logical location and interact invisibly in the background with multiple applications. Distribution with the invisible interaction taking place in the background further complicates the identification of potentially insane resources.

All devices in the infrastructure must be in place and in working condition during the investigation. Since the data in the cloud infrastructure is stored in different locations, the integrity of the evidence may be impaired if any server is not active. Although there is a large infrastructure to search for investigation data in the cloud environment, the time frame is limited when the resources are accessible. Therefore, researches are carried out in a planned figure and serially. There should be no disruption to the operation of the cloud service during the forensic investigation on the public cloud. No harm should be caused to other users who are not in the investigation queue. Providing access to personal data during the forensic period is within the scope of the law. During the investigation, the ways in which the said data will be accessed and how they will be processed are determined within the framework of the law and personal data is protected. The data is only examined by the investigation team and cannot be seen by third parties (Kaya, 2016:54).

2.7. Forensic Investigation of Computers Using Cloud Systems

Cloud forensics is defined as the application of scientific methods, technological applications and proven methods in order to identify, collect, protect, analyze and report electronic data in order to revive events that have arisen in cloud systems (Melland and Grance, 2014). Cloud systems are known as structures in which all the functions of the computer and many data perceived in the classical sense are located in the virtual environment. Before cloud systems products become widespread, users tend to store all their data on their own computers or storage units. However, new products have completely reversed the situation. From now on, everyone shares the content they want as well as storing them on the internet. In the examination of computers receiving cloud service, much more is needed than classical forensic methods. These services may also contain evidence on remote servers via internet connection as well as local computers. There are basically three cloud services:

- Cloud as Infrastructure Service (IaaS)

- Cloud as a Platform Service (PaaS)

- Cloud as a Software Service (SaaS)

The services given above are most commonly accessed by computers, mobile phones and tablet computers (Chung et al., 2012:81-95).

In classical forensics, when collecting evidence from computers, it is first evaluated according to whether the computers are turned on. In open computers, first of all, volatile data is detected and started to be collected. Later, the electrical connections of the computers are cut off and the steps to collect the evidence planned to be made on the computers that are turned off are applied (<https://www.ojp.gov/>).

In computers using cloud storage applications, firstly, a research is carried out on whether there are applications of cloud service providers in analyzing the computer. Passwords, login information or authorizations of users are determined through volatile data that will be detected in case the computers are turned on. With the obtained information, access to the data in the cloud storage area is provided and access to the evidence contained therein is provided (Chung et al., 2012:81-95).

When the techniques applied in classical forensic computing are used during cloud systems evidence research, difficulties are experienced due to some inherent characteristics of the systems in question. Within the scope of the structure of cloud systems, users are backed up to multiple servers in order not to lose their data, and it is not possible to collect data only in one center, and since these servers can be in different geographical locations, evidence is collected and restrictions are encountered (Pichan et al., 2015:38-57).

However, the software and hardware used in forensic investigations are classically designed to examine the evidence available in a physical figure. A few of these software offer the opportunity to make remote and identical copies or gather evidence over corporate or individual networks. In order to carry out this process, a small size software must be installed on the target system. If the data is changed, this method causes problems in terms of ensuring the integrity of the evidence. Among the methods of obtaining madness from cloud systems is logging into the system with the login information of the suspicious person. With this method, the situation of changing the data in the figure, which will be equivalent to opening a closed computer in classical forensics without write protection, is evaluated as it is connected to the real

system via the internet. Along with these two methods, there is a risk of claiming the data to be changed in court, since it involves interfering with the system used by the suspect.

There are studies showing that a copy of the data stored in cloud systems can be obtained by means of the aforementioned methods and similar methods, and there are some drawbacks of these processes.

- First of all, it is not possible to ensure the integrity of the evidence.
- It is not possible to access the system without write protection.
- Software for collecting evidence from cloud systems is not common.
- The methods used were not accepted as approved methods in the evaluation of software and hardware.
- Exact copying of all physical areas in the cloud is not seen as a practical application in large-scale systems.
- Since the copied copy does not contain the deleted fields, it is not a one-to-one copy as understood from classical forensics.
- The data in the cloud can be copied to more than one place on the servers, and the completeness of the copies cannot be expressed in a clear figure (Grispos et al., 2012:28-48).

In the future, the software that can be accepted by the courts in question, as well as the production of software that can provide an opportunity to be made in a figure in accordance with legal procedures, or through cloud service providers, evidence collection services for judicial units are provided over the cloud through a special interface for law enforcement personnel. In this transition period, there is a need to systematically bring the methods developed for the development of some methods that will not have problems in a legal figure for law enforcement personnel regarding the acts committed by criminal individuals.

Despite all the difficulties, suspected computers contain many different kinds of evidence. In order to overcome the situation of service providers not sharing user data in order to avoid legal problems, forensic experts collect evidence from the computers that receive the cloud service, while firstly, evidence is collected from the seized computers. Then, it has been tried to be associated with the collected evidences and the data that can be accessed from the cloud storage area in an environment open to all. In this association, the status of logging in from the computers in which the cloud storage area of the investigation was confiscated, and the status of uploading the files under investigation can also be determined

2.8. Related Studies

In Say's (2006) study, it was aimed to collect evidence from crime scenes where science crimes were committed, to send the evidence to the data analysis laboratory and to show the ways to examine it there, and to correct the mistakes made by the field personnel. Within the scope of the study, in the data laboratory where electronic evidence is obtained and digital evidence is examined, the precautions and techniques that should be taken in order not to spoil and obscure the evidence are emphasized.

In the study of Çiçek (2008), it was aimed to examine the legal, technical and practical problems in Turkey regarding cyber crimes. The study contributed to the development of forensic skills, the establishment of an accredited forensic laboratory, and the internationally valid cybercrime mechanism.

In the study of Tekin (2019), it was aimed to investigate the contributions of open source use to forensics and the problems in comparing forensic applications. However, within the scope of the study, predictions and recommendations about the future were made within the scope of applications encountered in forensic information applications. In line with the purpose, the concept of open source was defined and compared with closed code and commercial code.

Sakarya (2019) aimed to conduct a comprehensive research on the use of digital technologies in judicial institutions, the use of digital technologies, and the digital literacy rates of personnel working in ordinary institutions. According to the data provided as a result of the study, it has been determined that the level of digital literacy

of the personnel working in judicial institutions is low. However, it was observed that there was no significant difference between men and women in digital literacy levels.

In Öcal's (2022) study, the structure, architecture, infrastructure, service and distribution figures of cloud computing systems discussed the advantages and disadvantages of cloud computing in a detailed figure. In addition, attacks on security, privacy and privacy in the system and solutions for threats were emphasized. In the study, researches on cryptographic types were carried out.

Kolat (2023), in his study, aimed to characterize the contracts between cloud service providers and users from a legal point of view and to examine the responsibilities of service providers arising from breach of data security within the scope of contract law. As a result of the evaluation made within the scope of the study, current legislation, jurisprudence and opinions in the doctrine are given.

In the scope of the study of Çelik (2022), it is aimed to determine the numerical evidence that should be found at the crime scene when the judicial law enforcement duties intervene in an incident, to examine the said evidence and to examine the connection between these numerical evidences.

CONCLUSION

With cloud computing systems, individuals and institutions can access information from any location with multiple smart devices in the current period, thanks to the internet, and it has become easier to use many features such as sharing and storage. In addition, cloud computing platforms have lower costs compared to other systems, providing a more convenient, easy-to-access, scalable, more flexible and secure environment. In addition to the infrastructure created by cloud computing, together with the platform and software services, applications are created in a faster figure with less effort. In addition, it was ensured that systems with a secure structure, low cost and scalable quality were established with fewer hardware devices. Along with the distribution models in cloud computing, it provides the opportunity to develop platforms, software and applications that every individual can access when requested, as well as creating a confidential, closed and safer structure in the systems together with sensitive data. Institutions and organizations that use or start using cloud computing have seen that cloud computing has a very strong structure and has many benefits. Over time, high data increases, and the maintenance and management of the said data and the important qualities that the personnel who perform these actions and the traditional IT infrastructure cannot offer, lead institutions to cloud computing infrastructure. The fact that there are legal gaps in the security of data in countries and the opportunities offered by cloud computing have directed cybercriminals to cloud computing platforms. With the increase in forensic crimes committed on the cloud system, traditional forensic computing has required a restructuring in a figure. Obtaining digital evidence through cloud computing systems is more complex than traditional systems. Coordination with mutual responsibilities between cloud service providers and service users is very important in obtaining evidence within the scope of Ali investigations. Service level agreements between service providers and users determine the responsibilities of the parties. Choosing the right service providers is also important, as cloud customers face many problems in obtaining evidence in any forensic investigation process. It is necessary that the services provided during the investigation continue without interruption, that there is no effect on the users who are not the target of the investigations, that the confidentiality of the data is protected.

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